

African Red Slip Ware digital (ARS3D) - The Portal

Working Paper

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About this document

This document describes the outcome of the ARS3D project - the Portal, which is available at <http://ars3d.rgzm.de>. The portal consists of a landing page, several search pages, an object detail page, the object 3D viewer and the comparison viewer.

Introduction

The iconography of the decoration on so-called African Red Slip Ware (ARS) is pivotal to understanding Late Antique iconology. The collaborative project between i3mainz and the RGZM presents this artefact category in an innovative and sustainable way through 3D digitisation.

Background

Characteristic of the North African bowls, plates and jugs are their pictorial decorations applied mainly by appliqués and stamps. As mass-produced image carriers and everyday objects, the ARS spread throughout the empire.

The range of motifs includes mythological scenes as well as scenes from the Old and New Testament, circus, arena and hunting scenes as well as fish and plant motifs. The appliqués-decorated pottery thus provides insights into Late Antique imagination and its changes, as well as into the economic history of the period between the 3rd and 5th centuries AD in North Africa.

Previous documentation methods were not able to capture the objects and their decoration in an adequate way. The digital recording of the RGZM's collections by 3D scans allows to compare potentially identical appliqués and to assign them to their negative forms and the corresponding stamps.

Whereas vessel curvature previously falsified the assignment of appliqués and models, 3D analysis and visualisation tools now allow a comparison. Metadata created for each object increases the effectiveness and accuracy of determining image context and content. Issues related to the production of the ARS and the process flows within the workshops can be investigated through the analysis of the 3D data.

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What did we do?

In the ARS3D-project, the following main tasks were performed:

- 3D Digitalisation
- Semantic Modelling
- Semantic Annotation
- Research Software Engineering
- Comparison Analysis
- Data Publishing

The 324 ARS objects in the RGZM's collection were 3D digitised using structured light projection scanners. An ontology was developed to describe the meta- and para-data and the archaeological annotation in a semantic modelled graph. Tools arising from research software engineering, such as input forms, 3D visualisations and comparative analyses, can be used to systematically analyse and process the RGZM ARS collection.

3D Scanning

Textured 3D models are available for all ARS objects in the RGZM's collection.

The high-precision 3D data acquisition of the objects was carried out with the ATOS Triple Scan structured light scanner from GOM. After processing the scan data, a 3D model is created. In order to provide these 3D models with a realistic surface, the originals were photographed from different perspectives with the Nikon D800 system camera. After the generation of the 3D models and the subsequent connection of the 3D model and the photos with each other, a true color textured 3D model for each object is available for further analysis.

2.5D Height Image Generation

To visualise features of a 3D model, such as appliqués or appliqué moulds, these have been projected into a plane and processed into a 2.5D image.

For better visualisation, a height correction is applied to features on a non-plane object surface. This height correction is an approximation based on the object surface of the carrier object surrounding the feature.

Comparison

The comparison includes (1) Geometrical Comparison and (2) the Archaeological Comparison aspects.

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Geometrical Comparison

Geometric comparison of features by deformation analysis using image processing methods.

2.5D height images can be aligned to each other using iterative image processing. For this purpose, areas of a 2.5D image in the size of 5x5 mm and 10x10 mm are searched within a second 2.5D image. This enables the detection and visualisation of differences in position and height. A logical process can give a rough estimation if two 2.5D images are similar based on residuals in the position. Together with a viewer this should help to answer archaeological questions.

Jonas Veller / Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Archaeological Comparison

Archaeological comparison of features based on a semantically modelled rule-set.

The archaeological comparison is based on the geometric data. Generally, local and global differences or similarities are distinguished. If conspicuousness is observed, an evaluation of the reason follows, e.g. damage, modifications during the manufacturing process, additional material residues, etc. Depending on the reason and spread of the change, a rule-based statement on the similarity of two features is made. A veto - combined with a detailed explanation - may be applied if the professional observation is discrepant with the selected factors.

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Datamodel and Annotation

The data is stored in a graph structure. The classes, relations and rules are modelled in an ontology.

The ARS3D project carries out the following main tasks:

- Semantic Modelling
- Semantic Annotation
- Comparison Analysis
- Data Publishing

The developed ontology uses CIDOC CRM and various extensions. The data mainly consists of objects (E24), on which e.g. applications (features, E25) can be found. These objects can be described semantically, e.g. by the shape or time epoch. Features are described with observations, e.g. a human type man standing and wearing a beard. These observations lead to interpretations whose arguments can be observations.

- [Ontology](#)
- [Graph Data](#)
- [Comparison Data](#)
- [Images](#)
- [Linked Open Data](#)
- [Wikidata](#)

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Technology

In the ARS3D project we use the following technologies:

- modelling using OWL
- datastorage in a RDF4J Triplestore
- Docker IT-Architecture
- 3D-HOP 3D-viewer
- Structured light scanner Atos Triple Scan of the company GOM
- SLR Camera Nikon D800

Long-term archiving & iDAI.Objects

The 3D models are archived for the long term at the DAI and published in its database iDAI.objects. The 3D models of the entire ARS objects as well as associated metadata and images are archived at the DAI for the long term. The 3D models are published in its database iDAI.objects ([arachne](#)).

Team

Institutions

- i3mainz - Institut für Raumbezogene Informations- und Messtechnik
- Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum Leibniz-Forschungsinstitut für Archäologie

Funding

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Publications (Excerpt)

Scientific Talks

- Florian Thiery, Ashish Karmacharya, & Louise Rokohl. (2019, April). ARS3D - Documenting facts and interpretations of African Red Slip Ware. Presented at the Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (KraKAA), Krakow, Poland: Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2648217>
- A. Karmacharya, L. Rokohl, F. Thiery, African Red Slip Ware als Graph: Modellierung in CIDOC-CRM im ARS3D-Projekt. Graph Technologies in the Humanities 2019, Mainz, Germany, 19th January 2019. Video: <https://t1p.de/9m0a>.
- G. Heinz, L. Rokohl., 3D-Dokumentation von Sammlungsobjekten und Datenanalyse im RGZM. 9. Workshops der AG CAA Deutschland, Wilhelmshaven, Germany, 23rd September 2019.

Paper

- Justus, C., Atorf, P. und Boochs, F.: Gewinnung realitätsnaher virtueller Modelle als Grundlage für die Erkennung von Ähnlichkeiten. Photogrammetrie-Laserscanning -Optische 3D-Messtechnik, Wichmann, 2019, ISBN 978-3-87907-660-4.

- Florian Thiery, Ashish Karmacharya, & Louise Rokohl. (2019, April). ARS3D - Documenting facts and interpretations of African Red Slip Ware. Presented at the Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (KakCAA), Krakow, Poland: Zenodo. [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2648217](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2648217).
- F. Thiery, L. Rokohl, A. Karmacharya, Semantic modelling and publishing African Red Slip Ware as Linked Data. Computer Applications & Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (in review).
- C. Justus, L. Rokohl, F. Boochs, Similarity analysis of African Red Slip Ware (ARS) with modern 3D and 2D processing techniques. Computer Applications & Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (in review).

Internet

- [Open Science Framework Project](#)
- [GitLab RLP Repositories](#)
- [Zenodo Community](#)
- [Wikidata Project](#)

Portal

The ARS3D-Portal is accessible via <http://ars3d.rgzm.de>. Starting from a Landing Page containing project information the user can access the data by four faceted search interfaces. On top of that, each object is represented by a detail page containing meta- and para-information, as well as information on related features, interpretations and comparisons. The 3D data is analysable using the 3DHOP framework; the comparisons using Leaflet technologies.

Search

The portal contains four faceted search interfaces:

- Objects: <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/objectSearch.htm>
- Features: <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/featureSearch.htm>
- Interpretations: <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/interpretationSearch.htm>
- Comparisons: <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/comparisonSearch.htm>

On the top left you can find a style menu to set the sort attribute (label or inventory number), the result style (boxes or list), the active filters (if selected, click to delete filter), a substring search for label and identifier as well as a selection of keywords for filtering. The page reloads on every event and shows the resulting number of entities for a specific query. With a click on the displayed box, the object detail page will be opened in a new window.

SORT ATTRIBUTE

label inventory number

RESULT STYLE ATTRIBUTE

boxes list

ACTIVE FILTER

FILTER LABEL & IDENTIFIER

FILTER KEYWORDS

Object Search

The object search (total count 325) gives you the possibility to look for specific objects with special keywords related to the ontology as faceted search (P1 AND P2 AND Px):

- Object Properties
 - Type (African Red Slip Ware: 271; Manufacturing Object: 54)
 - Shape (e.g. bowl: 157; rectangular dish: 44, mould: 42)
 - Material (clay: 279; plaster: 42)
 - Condition (fragmented: 164; reconstructed: 66; complete: 52)
 - Manufacturing Type (potter wheel: 179; mould made: 70)
 - Findspot (unknown: 325)
 - Residence (RGZM: 325)
 - Period (e.g. Late Antiquity, 310/320-430/450 AD: 140)
 - Group (e.g. bowl with dolphin and erot: 3)
 - Statement: Hayes, Atlante (e.g. Hayes 53A: 141; Hayes 56: 37; Atlante X A1a: 15)
- External Properties
 - Getty AAT (e.g. [clay](#): 279; [bowls \(vessels\)](#): 157)
 - Wikidata (e.g. [plate](#): 7; [jug](#) 6)
- Feature Properties
 - Type (e.g. Applique (positive): 141; Mould: 37)
 - Manufacturing Type (e.g. applied decorated: 167; stamped decorated: 24)
 - Statement: Armstrong, Hayes, Löwenstein, Atlante (e.g. Armstrong 9.3A-D:10)
 - Observation Item Class (e.g. Human: 163; Animal: 119; Plant: 89)
 - Observation Item (e.g. man: 124; tunic: 51; erot: 36; palm-branch: 35)
 - Observation Activity (e.g. holding object: 123; standing: 70; jumping: 35)
 - Observation Condition (e.g. dressed: 68; naked: 65; bearded: 48)

This example search above shows the results for ARS Objects with the properties: African Red Slip Ware (type), bowl (shape), complete (condition) and Plant (observation item class).

The resultset contains six objects: 6 clay (material), 6 potter wheel (manufacturing type), 6 unknown (findspot), 6 RGZM (residence), 5 Late Antiquity > 310/320-430/450 AD (period), 1 Late Antiquity > 4. century AD (period), no group, 5 Hayes 53A (statement), 1 Hayes 67 (statement), 6 clay/bowls (vessels) (Getty AAT), 6 bowl/clay (Wikidata), 5 Applique (positive) (Feature Type), 2 Applique (positive) Part (Feature Type), 1 Applique (negative) (Feature Type), 5 applied decorated (Feature Manufacturing Type), 1 stamped decorated (Feature Manufacturing Type), several Armstrong / Atlante / Hayes / Löwenstein Feature statements, several Observation items such as Plant, Human, Animal related to activities and conditions.

Feature Search

The feature search (total count 1173) gives you the possibility to look for specific features on objects with special keywords related to the ontology as faceted search (P1 AND P2 AND Px):

- Feature Properties
 - Type (e.g. Applique (positive): 467; Mould: 171)
 - Material (clay: 926; plaster: 244)
 - Manufacturing Type (e.g. applied decorated: 427; stamped decorated: 170)
 - Statement: Armstrong, Hayes, Löwenstein, Atlante (e.g. Armstrong 9.3A-D:26)
 - Observation Item Class (e.g. Human: 264; Animal: 275; Plant: 208)
 - Observation Item (e.g. man: 176; tunic: 76; erot: 41; palm-branch: 80)
 - Observation Activity (e.g. looking to the left: 215; standing: 100)
 - Observation Condition (e.g. dressed: 99; naked: 90; bearded: 75)
 - Group (e.g. palmettes: 7; Jonah cycle: 5)
 - Interpretation (e.g. wedding of Thetis: 8; Venus in temple: 4)
- External Properties
 - IconClass (e.g. man: 176; fishes: 58)
 - Getty AAT (e.g. tunics: 76; trees: 30)
 - Wikidata (e.g. lion: 42; flower: 28)
- Object Properties
 - Shape (e.g. bowl: 390; rectangular dish: 203, mould: 241)
 - Statement: Hayes, Atlante (e.g. Hayes 53A: 332; Hayes 56: 192)

ARS3D Feature Search

TOTAL 3 ARS FEATURES LOADED!

SOFT ATTRIBUTES
 label inventory number

RESULT STYLE ATTRIBUTES
 boxes list

ACTIVE FILTERS

Feature type
 Applique (positive)

interpretation
 Hercules

FROM LABELS & DESCRIPTIONS

FILTER KEYWORDS

Feature Type
 Feature Material
 Feature Manufacturing Type
 Feature Statement
 Feature Observation Item Class
 Feature Observation Item
 Feature Observation Activity
 Feature Observation Condition
 Feature Group

Hercules killing the lion

Q.39676 [bowl with Hercules killing the Nemean lion]

bow and arrow

Q.39676 [bowl with Hercules killing the Nemean lion]

club

Q.39676 [bowl with Hercules killing the Nemean lion]

This example search above shows the results for ARS Features with the properties: Applique (positive) (type), and Hercules (interpretation).

The resultset contains three features: 3 Applique (positive) (type), 3 clay (material), 3 applied decorated (manufacturing type), 1 statements Armstrong 1.45/1.44/8.107 and Löwenstein Hercules X, 2 Ancient weapons, 1 Animal / Human / Mythological or Religious Character (Observation Item Class) in detail man, lion, Hercules, club, arrow, bow, related to the holding, killing and looking to the left activities having beardless, muscular, naked, and held by figure left conditions, Hercules (group), bowl (shape), Hayes 53A (object statement), das well as several IconClass, Getty AAT and Wikidata references.

Interpretation Search

The interpretation search (total count 165) gives you the possibility to look for specific interpretations of features on objects with special keywords related to the ontology as faceted search (P1 AND P2 AND Px):

- Properties
 - Observation Item (e.g. man: 107; club: 16; altar: 5)
 - Statement: Armstrong, Löwenstein, Atlante (e.g. Armstrong 9.3A-D: 12)

The screenshot displays the ARS3D Interpretation Search interface. On the left, a sidebar contains the following elements: a header 'TOTAL 4 INTERPRETATIONS LOADED!', a 'SORT ATTRIBUTE' section with 'label' selected, a 'RESULT STYLE ATTRIBUTE' section with 'boxes' selected, and an 'ACTIVE FILTERS' section showing 'Feature statement Armstrong 8.104'. Below this is a search bar with the text 'enter search string' and a 'FILTER KEYWORDS' section with 'Feature Observation Item' and 'Feature Statement' listed. The main area shows four 3D model thumbnails arranged in a 2x2 grid. Each thumbnail has a title and a description: top-left 'Hercules 0.40805 [bowl with Hercules]', top-right 'Hercules 0.40833 [bowl with woman and helmet]', bottom-left 'Hercules and Mars battling over the ... 0.40808 [bowl with man and sword]', and bottom-right 'Minerva 0.40833 [bowl with woman and helmet]'. Each thumbnail shows a grey 3D model of a fragment of an ancient artifact.

This example search above shows the results for ARS Interpretations with the property: Armstrong 8.104.

The resultset contains four interpretations: 3 man, 1 woman, 1 club, 4 Armstrong 8.104, 4 Löwenstein Hercules im Kampf mit Mars um die Leiche des Kyknos I.

Abb. 32. Szenische Darstellung Hercules im Kampf gegen den Löwen. Rekonstruktionszeichnung.

cf. Löwenstein (2015), p. 465.

Literary Figures

8.104 *Hercules and Mars Battling over the Body of Kyknos* On the left is Hercules, facing front, naked and brandishing a dagger above his head in his right hand; a lion-skin is draped over his left shoulder. On the left, Minerva restrains him, placing her right hand on his raised right arm. Opposite Hercules is Mars, seen from the back, also naked, with a mantle draped over his left shoulder. He wears a crested helmet, and holds a dagger in his right hand and a large round shield in his left between himself and Hercules. On the right, a draped female figure restrains him, placing her left hand in his right wrist. In the center, above the shield, the head and shoulders of Mercury appears, with wings above the forehead and a mantle draped over his left shoulder and fastened on the right by a round pin. On the ground between Hercules and Mars is the broken naked body of Kyknos. It occurs on two fragments (53.80, 53.143) and on the floor of a restored bowl (53.67).

cf. Armstrong (1993), pp. 191-192.

Comparison Search

The comparison search (total count 469) gives you the possibility to look for specific feature comparisons with special keywords related to the ontology as faceted search:

- Properties
 - Overall Estimation (borderline case: 216; different: 165; equal: 88)
 - Archaeological Estimation (borderline case: 203; different: 140; equal: 126)
 - Geometrical Estimation (borderline case: 243; different: 190; equal: 36)
 - Global Conspicuity (Wear or Damage: 70; Shift or Twist: 47)
 - Local Conspicuity (Shift or Twist: 115, Damage: 43; Manual Modification_ 7; Additional Material Scraps: 2)
 - Geometrical Disruption: (No: 444, Yes: 25)

The screenshot displays the ARS3D Comparison Search interface. On the left, a sidebar contains filters for 'TOTAL 6 COMPARISONS' (LOADED!), 'SORT ATTRIBUTE' (label selected), 'RESULT STYLE ATTRIBUTE' (boxes selected), and 'ACTIVE FILTERS' (overall estimation, equal, archaeological estimation, borderline case). Below these are search input fields and a list of filter categories: Overall Estimation, Archaeological Estimation, Geometrical Estimation, Global Conspicuity, Local Conspicuity, and Geometrical Disruption. The main area shows six comparison results in a 2x3 grid, each with a 3D visualization and a title: 41360_wreath_4_wreath_7, 41360_wreath_7_wreath_6, 41361_satyr_3_satyr_1, 41363_lioness_5_41364_lioness_4, 41363_lioness_7_lioness_11, and 41363_lioness_8_41364_lioness_4. Each result includes the text 'EQUAL SCORE 2 ARCH-BORDERLINE CASE GEO-EQUAL'.

This example search above shows the results for ARS comparisons with the properties: equal (overall estimation) and borderline case (archaeological estimation).

The resultset contains six comparisons: 6 equal (geometrical estimation), 3 Shift or Twist (global conspicuity), 2 Damage (local conspicuity), 1 Shift or Twist (local conspicuity), 6 No (geometrical disruption).

41363 lioness 7 lioness 11

Comparison Viewer of comparison "41363_lioness_7_lioness_11"¹

The figure above shows the comparison "41363 lioness 7 lioness 11" of the features "lioness7" and "lioness 11" of object "0.41363", with a dimension [mm] of 59.625 x 27.975 and a max. height deviation range [mm] of 1.08 to 0.9.

The overall estimation is "equal", the logic process was not overruled. The automatic geometric estimation results as "equal" with no geometric interference. The archaeological estimation results as "borderline case" with a global conspicuity (shift or twist) and no local conspicuity. The features are placed on the same object. All of this results in an overall score of 2 - where the archaeological score 1 (0=different; 3=equal).

¹ https://ars3d.rgzm.de/comparisonviewer/index.htm?comparison_id=399ed796-c17f-4c4b-86cc-64929fc4c356

Object Main Page

The “Object Main Page” contains all details for an African Red Slip Ware Digital (ARS3D) Object: object Data (archaeological paradata / annotations), meta data, project data, scan/3D-model data, as well as related features, interpretations and comparisons, if available. With this page you can enter the 3D viewer, the comparison viewer as well as the scan metadata JSON files.

bowl with Abraham and Isaac (O.40573)

Object Data go to 3D model	
African Red Slip ware	object type
bowl	shape
clay	material
complete	condition type
potter wheel	manufacturing type
unknown	findspot
Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum	residence
Late Antiquity (310/320-430/450 AD)	period
False	group
Hayes: Hayes 53A from Hayes (1972), p.78-80	statement

Object Data of O.40573²

OBJECT FEATURES

Feature [go to 3D model](#)

Abraham	label
Applique (positive)	feature type
applied decorated	manufacturing type
2020-06-25T19:41:30.955+02:00	creation date
Abraham: bearded,holding,holding object,holding sword,looking to the left,standing	observation
man: bearded,holding,holding object,holding sword,looking to the left,standing	observation
short belted tunic	observation
tunic	observation
Armstrong 8.207	statement
Löwenstein männl. Gewandfigur II b	statement

Feature [go to 3D model](#)

Isaac	label
Applique (positive)	feature type
applied decorated	manufacturing type
2020-06-25T19:43:45.345+02:00	creation date
Isaac: beardless,carrying,carrying bag,looking to the right,standing	observation
man: beardless,carrying,carrying bag,looking to the right,standing	observation
short belted tunic	observation
tunic	observation
Armstrong 8.208	statement
Löwenstein männl. Gewandfigur II a	statement

Two features data boxes of O.40573³

² <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/object.htm?id=ars3do:95c8cc98-06a8-4bb6-a85b-fcc93c98689f>

³ <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/object.htm?id=ars3do:95c8cc98-06a8-4bb6-a85b-fcc93c98689f>

mould lions (O.41363)

Object Data [go to 3D model](#)

Manufacturing Object	object type
mould	shape
plester	material
n/a	condition type
n/a	manufacturing type
unknown	findspot
n/a	residence
n/a	period
false	group

Object Data of O.41363⁴

Feature [go to 3D model](#)

lioness 1	label
Mould	feature type
n/a	manufacturing type
2020-08-29T18:11:46.976+02:00	creation date
lioness: looking to the left,running	observation
Armstrong 6.43	statement

Feature [go to 3D model](#)

lioness 10	label
Mould	feature type
n/a	manufacturing type
2020-08-29T18:25:26.439+02:00	creation date
lioness: looking to the left,running	observation
Armstrong 6.43	statement

Two features data boxes of O.41363⁵

Comparison [go to viewer](#)

41363_lioness_7_lioness_11	label
equal	estimation overall
2	score
borderline case	estimation archaeology
equal	estimation geometry

Comparison [go to viewer](#)

41363_lioness_8_41364_lioness_4	label
equal	estimation overall
2	score
borderline case	estimation archaeology
equal	estimation geometry

Two comparisons of O.41363⁶

⁴ <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/object.htm?id=ars3do:61b55d27-3778-4b41-bd0c-7acc1cae9d02>

⁵ <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/object.htm?id=ars3do:61b55d27-3778-4b41-bd0c-7acc1cae9d02>

⁶ <https://ars3d.rgzm.de/object.htm?id=ars3do:61b55d27-3778-4b41-bd0c-7acc1cae9d02>

Viewer Components

The ARS3D Portal provides two major viewer components: a 3D-Viewer for the scanned ARS objects based on 3DHOP⁷ and the Comparison-Viewer to show results of geometrical comparisons based on Leaflet⁸.

3D-Viewer

The 3D-Viewer shows the scanned ARS object in a web browser using the 3DHOP framework. The user functionalities can be divided in three sections: 3D analysis tools (left side), object / feature annotation tools (right side), and the 3D model itself with annotated features (centre), see figure below.

The 3D view of O.39676 using 3DHOP

The 3D analysis tools contain buttons to go back to the initial view, zoom in and out, select predefined views, rotate object, light control, enable/disable texture and to measure.

⁷ <https://www.3dhop.net/>

⁸ <https://leafletjs.com/>

3D view of O.39676 using 3DHOP and analysing tools

The figure above⁹ shows O.39676 without the texture, a spotlight on the right side of the bowl, as well as a measurement of Hercules' waist.

The object / feature annotation tools on the right-right side enables the user to show the objects, features, feature groups, and interpretation annotation- and paradata. On top of that, details of single features can be visualised in a box on the bottom right by enabling the button, see figure below.

⁹ based on https://ars3d.rgzm.de/viewer.htm?model_id=ars3do:57052b95-ca87-4d40-b59c-7c4128f78b23

Comparison-Viewer

The Comparison Viewer shows details and visualisations of a geometrical and archaeological feature comparison.

Comparison Viewer of comparison "41363_lioness_7_lioness_11"¹⁰

¹⁰ https://ars3d.rqzm.de/comparisonviewer/index.htm?comparison_id=399ed796-c17f-4c4b-86cc-64929fc4c356

The initial view (see figure above) shows the two features in two “map views”.

Move the slider to change the opacity of the overlay layers of the **left windows**

Opacity Value: 100%

The layer symbol provides several options to overlay the left 2.5D image of a feature with (1) the second feature, (2) the translation residuals and (3) the height difference image.

Move the slider to change the opacity of the overlay layers of the **left windows**

Opacity Value: 50%

Beside this shown geometrical attributes, all details for the comparisons are displayed in several sections:

- comparison overall (estimation, veto)
- scores (overall, archaeological)
- geometric information (dimension, max. height deviation range)
- automatic geometric estimation (estimation, geometric interference)
- archaeological estimation (estimation, global / local conspicuity)

Comparison Overall

equal	estimation overall
No	logic process overruled
-	veto reason

Scores

2	score overall
1	score (archaeology)

Geometric Information

59.625 x 27.975	dimension [mm]
-1.08 to 0.9	max. height deviation range [mm]

Automatic Geometric Estimation

equal	geometric estimation
No	geometric interference

Archaeological Estimation

borderline case	archaeological estimation
Yes	global conspicuity
Shift or Twist (global)	global conspicuity detail
No	local conspicuity
Yes	same object

Comparison Details of comparison "41363_lioness_7_lioness_11"¹¹

¹¹ https://ars3d.rqzm.de/comparisonviewer/index.htm?comparison_id=399ed796-c17f-4c4b-86cc-64929fc4c356

Identifier and Links

Content	URL / Identifier
OSF Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: 10.17605/OSF.IO/6HJ7G
GitLab-RLP Repositories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://gitlab.rlp.net/ars3d
Zenodo Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://zenodo.org/communities/ars3d/
Graph Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5642750
ARS3D Ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5642891 https://ars3d.pages.gitlab.rlp.net/ars3d-ontology/
Comparison Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5647827
Portal / Web-Application	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://ars3d.rgzm.de DOI: 10.17605/OSF.IO/P5TKW
API	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://java-dev.rgzm.de/arspi DOI: 10.17605/OSF.IO/WRJ7K
Comparison Script	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5647864
Images	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://gitlab.rlp.net/ars3d/ars3d-images DOI: 10.17605/OSF.IO/UM3AN Objects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5645179 Features <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5645236 Comparisons <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5645253
Linked Open ARS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://github.com/RGZM/ars-lod DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5722941
ARS in Wikidata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wikidata:WikiProject_African_Red_Slip_Ware_Digital

Bibliografie

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